

Software Sustainability at the eScience Center

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Our Sustainability Vision

A Sustainable Research Software Ecosystem to Accelerate Discovery & Innovation

The development and application of research software has become a critical component of the scientific method. Most research projects rely on dedicated software to analyse experimental results, gain scientific insight or communicate these findings to the rest of the scientific community. Modern research can no longer be performed without research software.

With this increased importance, comes increased scrutiny and demands regarding the reliability and availability of these widely used scientific instruments. For research software to fulfil its mission, it should be easily accessed by the scientific community and provide results that the community can trust. In other words, these tools should endure the test of time: they should be sustainable.

The importance of research software sustainability has been acknowledged by different initiatives such as [ADORE](#), [the UNESCO recommendation on Open Science](#) the [Software Sustainability Institute](#), the [FAIR Software](#) initiative and the multiple [peer-reviewed journals](#) dedicated to software. These initiatives call for funding organizations to support not only the development of innovative research software but also the long-term maintenance of these essential tools.

Such funding instruments invariably lead to an increased return on investment by allowing researchers to reuse openly accessible software across projects and disciplines. Researchers can then focus on research and spend less time developing the tool they need, which ultimately accelerates discovery and innovation.

Benefits of Software Sustainability for Research

Research software takes many shapes and forms, from analysis scripts for personal use to large scale computational tools shared among many. These different types of software have different requirements in terms of sustainability level. Software Sustainability, i.e. the capacity of a software to endure in an ever-changing environment, is an inherently multidimensional concept. We focus here on two aspects of software sustainability, namely *Software Quality* and *Software Adoption*. We purposefully use these two components as focal points of our vision as they underpin two critical aspects of research: *quality creates trust while adoption stimulates cooperation*

Figure 1 Software sustainability map. Software Quality and Software Adoption define the sustainability level of a software. Dedicated actions can be defined to improve the quality and adoption of software towards sustainability.

Software Quality Creates Trust

The reproducibility crisis that science is facing not only undermines trust in academic research but also significantly slows down innovation. The considerable number of article retractions and other reports of unreproducible results significantly reduces opportunities for researchers to build on each other's work. By following [Research Software Best practices](#) and [Guides](#), ranging from documentation to validation, research software engineers can safeguard the validity of the results obtained using the tools they are developing. The development of an open-source ecosystem of high-quality research software offers a solution to improve trust in research and accelerate innovation.

Software Adoption Stimulates Cooperation

The best engineered research software remains of limited value if it is only used by its original developer. Depending on their scope, some tools have the potential to be shared among different research groups working on similar topics. The sharing of these tools within a community [stimulates cooperation](#) and therefore supports the development of new scientific ideas. To grow the user base of these tools, developers can organize [workshops](#) to present the functionalities of the tools and gain insight on potential requests from the target group. In addition, in order to foster a group of developers capable of maintaining the tool, it is very important to provide [research software engineering training](#) to the research community and to attract new research software engineers. The adoption of research software allows researchers to spend less time on crafting common tools and therefore dedicate more of their time to innovative research.

Championing Research Software Sustainability

As research software does not yet enjoy the notoriety of other research outputs, dedicated approaches are required to highlight the importance of software sustainability in an academic context.

Recognition for Research Software Engineers

Software sustainability is unachievable without dedicated research software engineers that can develop these tools and have enough resources to maintain them. The development of dedicated [research software engineers profile](#) helps promoting this non-traditional role in the academic landscape and work towards its recognition. In addition, dedicated instruments to raise awareness of the importance of software in academia, such as the [eScience Fellowships](#), help promoting the work of research staff engaged in software development. Supporting organizations such as the [Research Software Alliance](#), the International RSE Society and the [NL RSE community](#), allows research software engineers to connect with their peers, learn from each other experience and improve the recognition of the critical role they play in research.

Monitor and Highlight Software Impact

The [Research Software Directory](#) (RSD) allows not only to find software but also to put software in its context and to monitor its impact. This impact can be traced by collecting the direct citation of the software through its [Citation File Format](#) (CFF). This format allows to cite directly the repository where the software is hosted without requiring a journal publication. Software publications, for example in the [Journal of Open Source Software](#) or the [Journal of Open Research Software](#) can also add visibility to the software and increase its adoption and impact. Other tools such as [Fairtally](#), [howfairis](#) allows researchers, policy makers and funders to quickly assess the compliance of [software to the FAIR principles](#) and therefore highlight the investment in software sustainability made by organizations and research institutions.

Tailored Funding Solutions

As traditional funding instruments focus mostly on the development of research ideas, new dedicated funding instruments must be developed for software sustainability. Funding instruments must be created to improve the sustainability of existing software, i.e., going from point A to point B on the software sustainability map. Some calls are beginning to appear such as the calls from the [Netherlands eScience Center](#) and from the [DFG](#) dedicated to [software sustainability](#), or the more recently the creation of the [OpenScienceNL program](#). These instruments provide researchers and research software engineers opportunities to work on the quality and adoption of their software.

In addition, funding instruments that support the maintenance of a critical piece of software infrastructure must be developed. Without those instruments, software that has reached its targeted sustainability level will have difficulties keeping this level up and therefore risking wasting past investment made in increasing its

reliability and adoption. Such instruments could take the form of long-standing public funding agreements for tools critical for a large research community.

Practical Guide to Research Software Sustainability Projects

When starting a software sustainability project, the members of the research team including researchers and research software developers must define three important parameters:

1. **Current sustainability level:** the starting point of the project can be determined by a quick audit of the source code and the community of users and developers around it. [Research Software Health Checks](#) can be used to assess the current maturity of the software and the size and strength of its community.
2. **Target sustainability level:** As already mentioned earlier, not all research software has the ambition to reach the highest sustainability level. Determining which target level is best suited is critical to estimate the efforts required by the project. A comprehensive [Research Software Management plan](#) should be developed in agreement with the desired target level.
3. **Path to sustainability:** Different paths can be defined and adopted to reach the target sustainability level. Some projects should prioritize adoption to gauge the interest of the community while others should begin with quality improvement to improve the trust in the community. Defining this path is critical, but the best path to take might change during the journey towards sustainable software.

Figure 2 Example path towards software sustainability and the activities undertaken along the way.

Not all software requires the same efforts invested in their long-term sustainability. For example, the [practical guide to Software Management](#) define different tiers of software depending on their purpose, reliability and maintenance. Some software might require to be fully validated for correctness due to the critical nature of their output, while for others some basic testing might be enough. Similarly, some software might cater to the needs of a large group of researchers and have therefore great potential for adoption while others might fulfill the needs of a niche which does not make them less relevant for research. All these target sustainability levels are valid but require different efforts. The Netherlands eScience Center has invested in the sustainability of

different code base over the years. In some cases, the emphasis was on community adoption, in others on software quality and sometimes on both.

MUSCLE 3

MUSCLE3 is a coupling library for multiscale modeling. Due to the complex nature of the tool a lot of emphasis was put on software quality so that its output reaches a high level of reliability.

ESMValTool

Earth System Model Evaluation Tool

ESMValTool provides critical insight to a large community of climate scientists. In consequence both its quality and adoption have been addressed by a core community of developers

MATCHMS

MatchMS allows to port, process, clean, and compare mass spectrometry data and provide support for a growing community of bioinformatician. Community adoption was the priority of this project

Figure 3 Different software will start and end their sustainability path at various places depending on their scope. All these combinations are valid sustainability paths but might require distinct levels of investment and different expertise.